

Climate change and rice production in India

S. Mohandass, A. Abdul Kareem, and T. B. Ranganathan, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India; and M. J. Kropff, IRRI

Rice is India's most important cereal in terms of area and production. By about the year 2020, 65% more rice than the amount produced in 1989 will be needed in the world to meet the demands of the expanding human population (IRRI 1989).

Elevated CO₂ in the atmosphere will affect agricultural production by stimulating photosynthesis (Lemon 1993, Cure and Acock 1986) and improving water use efficiency of crops (Goudriaan and van Laar 1976, Sionit et al 1980). Increased CO₂ can also induce changes in climate, resulting in increased global average annual mean surface air temperature (IPPC Report, Houghton et al 1990). Such global warming is likely to affect agricultural production all over the world.

A crop growth simulation model, ORYZA 1 (Kropff et al 1993), was used to study the effect of temperature rise and elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentration on rice yields in India. The model was validated for the current climate conditions.

Effects of several combinations of temperature increases and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations on simulated yields were studied. The model simulated potential production, which is growth with ample nutrient supply and in the absence of damage by pests, diseases, and weeds.

A temperature increase of up to 2°C over the current level only marginally affected the length of the growing season (from 126 to 125 d). Grain yield, however, declined with a temperature increase of 7°C from 8.0 t/ha to 7.1 t/ha. Regarding locations, places such as Patancheru Bijarpur experienced comparatively greater yield decline (up to 20%) while Kapurthala and Madurai were affected only a little by the increase (see table).

An elevated level of atmospheric CO₂ generally led to an increase in the mean simulated potential yield. With the given weather data, the average increase for India was 11, 20, 28, 40, and 48% for 390, 444, 490, 590, and 680 ppm of atmos-

Effect of temperature rise on simulated grain yield (t/ha) of rice at 9 sites, India.

Site	Temperature rise (°C)						Mean
	0.0	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	
Aduthurai	7.94	7.85	7.80	7.70	7.57	7.35	7.70
Bijapur	6.74	6.47	6.32	6.03	5.86	5.93	6.22
Coimbatore	8.66	8.33	8.11	7.81	7.64	7.58	8.02
Cuttack	6.72	6.48	6.31	6.09	5.99	6.07	6.28
Hyderabad	8.91	8.93	8.61	8.30	8.10	8.14	8.50
Kapurthala	9.74	9.54	9.18	9.07	9.03	8.98	9.26
Pattambi	6.29	6.03	5.76	5.38	5.20	5.27	5.66
Madurai	8.64	8.61	8.53	8.37	8.18	7.89	8.37
Patancheru	8.20	7.92	7.62	7.22	6.91	6.72	7.43
Mean	7.99	7.80	7.58	7.33	7.16	7.10	

pheric CO₂, respectively, compared with the current level of 340 ppm.

The combined effect of doubled CO₂ (680 ppm) and temperature increase (4°C) led to an increase of about 2.5 t/ha (see figure) over current rice yields. In locations such as Kapurthala, Cuttack, and Madurai, the combined effect of doubled CO₂ and temperature increase had the beneficial result of offsetting the yield reduction caused by the temperature increase.

Photosynthesis and stomatal conductance in rice as affected by drought stress

Md. Jalaluddin and M. Price, School of Agriculture and Home Economics, University of Arkansas at Pine Bluff, Arkansas, USA; and R. H. Dilday, United States Department of Agriculture - Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARS), Stuttgart, Arkansas, USA

Agricultural activities, including rice production, may contribute to increased levels of greenhouse gases, such as CH₄ and N₂O, that lead to global warming. Methane emission from ricefields could be reduced if improved rice varieties

The Impact of climatic change (680 ppm CO₂ and/or 4°C increases) on rice yield at 9 locations in India.

REFERENCES CITED

- Cure J D, Acock B (1986) Crop responses to carbon dioxide doubling: a literature survey. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 38: 127-145.
- Goudriaan J, van Laar H H (1978) *Photosynthetica* 12:241-249.
- Houghton J T, Jenkins G J, Ephraums J J (1990) *Climate change. The IPCC Scientific Assessment.* Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- IRRI — International Rice Research Institute (1989) *IRRI towards 2000 and beyond.* P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. 80 p.
- Kropff M J, Van La H H, and ten Berge H T M (1993) *ORYZA1: an ecophysiological model for irrigated rice production.* P. O. Box 933 Manila, Philippines. p. 5.
- Lemon E R (1983) *CO₂ and plants, the response of plants to rising levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide.* Westview Press, Boulder, Colorado.
- Sionit N H, Hellmers H, Strain B R (1980) *Crop Sci.* 20:456-458. ■

having high yield potential under upland or nonflooded conditions are adopted.

Upland rice often experiences drought stress. Even a partial closure of stomata restricts gas exchange considerably and reduces assimilation rate (Dingkuhn et al 1989). For upland or nonflooded irrigated rice, elevated CO₂ may mitigate, in part, the adverse effects of water deficit. The objective of our study was to test rice cultivars of different origins and growth habits to determine varietal differences in rates of photosynthesis and stomatal conductance under upland conditions compared with lowland conditions.

We conducted two field experiments with four rice cultivars grown under